

Well-being and engagement: its implications for university policy on administrative employee's wellness program

John Michael D. Aquino¹, Jayson L. de Vera²

¹College of Teacher Education, Laguna State Polytechnic University, Santa Cruz, Philippines

²Faculty of Science and Technology, College of Teacher Development, Philippine Normal University, Manila, Philippines

Article Info

Article history:

Received Dec 31, 2024

Revised Jun 16, 2025

Accepted Jun 23, 2025

Keywords:

Administrative employee
Engagement and well-being
Professional development
University policies
Wellness program
Work-life balance

ABSTRACT

The well-being and engagement of administrative employees are critical to creating a productive and sustainable work environment. This study investigates causes of university administrative staff well-being and professional involvement. This study examines: i) employee engagement and well-being; ii) administrative employees' biggest workplace challenges; and iii) how wellness programs promote personal and professional progress. This study used a concurrent triangulation mixed-method research approach. Gallup's employee engagement survey found that 124 employees have overall favorable attitudes, with a composite mean score of 4.36 demonstrating moderate to high levels of engagement across key workplace indicators. The inconsistent recognition may have an impact on involvement, with the lowest mean of 3.80 and the biggest variability of 1.09. Meanwhile, semi-structured interviews were conducted with 12 administrative employees from a university in region 4A. The findings highlight factors influencing well-being, such as effective communication, work-life balance, positive office environments, and opportunities for promotion. Stress, heavy workloads, and insufficient recognition were seen to be significant challenges, whereas coping strategies including task prioritization, emotional regulation, and peer support were regarded as critical. The results show that well-being boosts commitment and productivity, whereas engagement improves mental health and job happiness. Universities must offer stress management, professional development, and recognition to improve results and staff engagement.

This is an open access article under the [CC BY-SA](https://creativecommons.org/licenses/by-sa/4.0/) license.

Corresponding Author:

John Michael D. Aquino

College of Arts and Sciences, Laguna State Polytechnic University

Santa Cruz, Laguna, Philippines

Email: johnmichael.aquino@lspu.edu.ph

1. INTRODUCTION

The mutual benefits model suggests that human resource management (HRM) should benefit both individuals and organizations [1]. Nevertheless, the main ideas in HRM theory and research continue to put too much weight on ways to improve performance, while employee concerns are only barely considered important. It concurs that improving performance outcomes through people management has been a central focus of HRM theory development [2]. Research shows that the field of HRM has only recently begun to pay attention to the correlation between employee engagement and performance, suggesting that this relationship may be the mechanism by which HRM practices affect both individual and organizational output. Human resource (HR) and organization development (OD) experts have the responsibility of boosting productivity and morale in the workplace [3]. They also emphasized the positive effects of perceived organizational

support and psychological capital (PsyCap) on employees' work-related happiness (i.e., work engagement), career-related happiness (i.e., career satisfaction), and life-related happiness (i.e., subjective well-being (SWB)). High levels of well-being were found to indicate high levels of commitment to the organization and a lower intention to leave. Engagement predicts happiness, while happiness predicts emotional commitment and inclinations to quit [4].

University administrative employees commonly report feeling underappreciated and unsupported in their jobs. They express feeling overlooked and underappreciated, with little help or recognition for their accomplishments [5]. Administrative employees at universities are usually asked to balance multiple responsibilities and a hefty workload. Administrative workers reported feeling overworked and worried [6]. They commonly complain about a lack of employment development opportunities and confusing career paths. Administrative employees acknowledged limited professional advancement opportunities and expressed dissatisfaction with the lack of possible career possibilities [7]. University administrative professionals regularly describe difficulties in establishing a work-life balance, which can lead to burnout and stress. They reported feeling pressurized and overworked, with little time for self-care or work-life balance [8]. There has been minimal research into the well-being of university administrative employees, with most studies focusing on faculty or students. Meanwhile, there is a lack of study on the experiences of administrative and support employees in higher education [9].

The study focuses heavily on professional engagement, as it seeks to investigate the factors that contribute to the engagement and well-being of university administrative employees. The project can provide valuable insights into how the university can enhance the working conditions and support mechanisms for its administrative employees, resulting in increased job satisfaction and productivity. Personal development is also a crucial aspect of this endeavor. This study investigates the influence of wellness programs on the personal growth and development of administrative employees. The project's findings could assist the university in designing wellness programs that foster personal growth and development, resulting in enhanced employees' performance and job contentment. In addition, the initiative has significant implications for the professional development of university administrative employees. The research investigates how wellness programs can contribute to the professional growth of employees by enhancing their skills, knowledge, and abilities. The project's findings could be used to develop training programs that support the professional development of employees, resulting in a more skilled and competent workforce. The significance of this project rests in its ability to address the university's research priorities by providing valuable insights into how wellness programs can promote professional engagement, personal growth, and professional development among administrative employees. This project's findings may have significant implications for the university's policies and practices, resulting in a more engaged, productive, and fulfilled workforce.

The study examines the following factors affecting university administrative staff well-being. Many studies show that workload and job demands can negatively affect health. Their well-being also depends on employment security, autonomy, work-life balance, and supervisor and colleague support. Administrative personnel struggle with heavy workloads, stress, and limited career advancement. Employee well-being and engagement are closely linked to employee happiness, motivation, and dedication. Therefore, it is crucial for institutions to foster involvement and provide administrative staff with opportunities to make decisions, engage in relevant projects, and receive recognition. Moreover, the researchers seek to answer the following objectives: explore Gallup's employee engagement work, determine the factors that influence the well-being of university administrative employees, identify how the administrative employees overcome the challenges that they encounter in their workplace, and know how engagement relates to employees' well-being. With these, the study offers significant insights to university management regarding the current state and demands of administrative employees to enhance workplace efficiency and contribute to the development of a wellness framework, programs, and activities aimed at assisting administrative employees in attaining a balanced well-being for enhanced productivity.

2. METHOD

The study utilized a concurrent triangulation mixed-methods approach which integrates both quantitative and qualitative data collection and analysis to more comprehensive understanding of university administrative personnel's well-being, work problem-solving, and engagement. This approach allows for the validation and corroboration of findings by comparing different data sources, enhancing the reliability and depth of the study's conclusion. Additionally, researchers examined the well-being and engagement of university administrative employees using a descriptive research methodology that included a survey and qualitative case studies. This design fully captured university administrative personnel experiences, opinions, and concerns [10], [11]. This strategy examined workplace features, personal coping strategies, institutional

regulations, and quality services. This study emphasizes the necessity for targeted policy actions to meet one university's administrative staff's particular issues and improve institutional performance.

The participants are administrative staff at a region 4A university. To ensure diversity, quantitative participants are university administrative employees picked by purposive sampling. The Kaiser-Meyer-Olkin (KMO) measure was used by the researchers to assess the adequacy of sample size for factor analysis [12]. The computed KMO measure results were 0.921, which falls in the "excellent" range. This indicates that the sample is highly adequate for analysis. Similarly, the survey included 124 administrative employees, 74 females and 50 males. Its age ranges from 23 to 62, showing a broad workload in university offices with young professionals and seasoned people. Meanwhile, the qualitative part requires administrative employees to have five years of service. This ensures participants understand and experience the university's projects, activities, and rules. This also allows individuals to demonstrate their university growth over time. Additionally, the participants are a broad mix of university administrative employees from several offices. Eight women and four men participated, with diverse experiences and qualifications. Most are between 26 and 50, with a significant mix of single and married people. Some participants are secretaries, but most are clerical. These variances enable a wide view of workplace involvement, problems, and well-being.

The quantitative part of the study utilized a survey to investigate what factors affect university administrative employees' well-being, how they handle work challenges, how engagement and well-being relate, and how to improve both. It is demonstrated that Cronbach's alpha of Gallup instrument was 0.82 which signifies that all the items of the Gallup had acceptable alphas because all the items have greater than 0.70 alphas [13]. Additionally, the 12-item Gallup Q12 questionnaire examines the relationship between employee engagement and performance management factors [14]. Thus, this study used a semi-structured questionnaire. The questionnaire covers these key ideas: i) factors affecting university administrative employees' well-being; ii) the biggest challenges they face and how they handle them; iii) strategies to improve their well-being; and iv) ways universities promote their well-being. This interview guide underwent expert validation through three field experts to ensure its relevance, clarity and alignment to the research objective. This also ensures the refinement of wordings and structure to enhance validity and reliability.

Before data collection, the Research Ethics Committees (REC) approved this study under REC number 2024-098 on April 1, 2024. Following a comprehensive validation by five field experts in physical education and mixed methods research, the questionnaire was piloted to assess its face validity and reliability. Based on the results, the researchers restructured the questionnaire for broader dissemination. Consent was obtained from the president of the participating university in region 4A. Additionally, interviews followed an initial approach to ensure a smooth and organized information-gathering process. Prior to the interviews and the validation procedure, consultations were held with the experts. The survey was administered in both online and paper-based formats to ensure accessibility, with a pre-survey briefing provided to explain the study's purpose and obtain informed consent.

This quantitative data was analyzed using descriptive statistics. The mean and standard deviation were calculated. This provides response distribution and involvement. However, qualitative data analysis requires coding acquired data to conceive it by categorizing it. Three coding schemes were used: open, axial, and selective. Line-by-line open coding highlights key concepts and phrases before dividing them into subcategories and categories. This lets researchers theorize or reflect on the data. Second, axial coding determines data links and connections. Selective coding, the third stage, finds the main category and links it to others.

3. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

This study's results offer significant insights into the determinants affecting the well-being and engagement of university administrative employees, along with the techniques employed to navigate workplace challenges. Administrative employees are essential to the institution's everyday operations, rendering their well-being and engagement crucial to overall organizational success. The results provide valuable insights into the experiences of administrative employees, highlighting the level of engagement at work, factors affecting their well-being, challenges they face, and the coping mechanisms they employ.

3.1. Employee engagement work

The results of Gallup's employee engagement work provide valuable insights into the factors influencing workplace productivity, employee satisfaction, and organizational success. Gallup's research highlights the critical role of engagement in driving performance, retention, and overall workplace well-being. Table 1 shows the findings of Gallup's employee engagement survey show that employees have generally positive attitudes, with a composite mean score of 4.36 indicating moderate to high levels of engagement across key workplace metrics. The highest-scoring items, such as "Does your supervisor, or someone at work, seem to care about you as a person?" (mean: 4.7). "At work, do you have the opportunity

to do what you do best every day?” The mean score of 4.55 indicates that individuals feel respected and can effectively apply their abilities in their employment. Items such as “Does the mission/purpose of your company make you feel your job is important?” yield consistent responses. (mean: 4.45, SD: 0.60), and “Are your associates committed to doing quality work?” (mean: 4.53, SD: 0.66), indicating a common understanding of organizational purpose and teamwork. However, the survey reveals a significant discrepancy in recognition practices, with the question “In the last seven days, have you received recognition or praise for doing good work?” having the lowest mean (3.80) and the greatest variability (SD: 1.09). This data suggests inconsistency in the way recognition is offered, which may have an impact on overall involvement. While the survey results highlight strong organizational practices in fostering personal care, strengths utilization, and teamwork, they also identify areas for improvement in ensuring consistent and meaningful recognition, as well as regular feedback and development opportunities for employees. The results underscore critical factors such as efficient communication, work-life equilibrium, nurturing surroundings, career advancement, and stress mitigation. Moreover, the findings elucidate how these employees confront challenges and discern chances for enhancing workplace dynamics. This section examines these themes, analyzing their consequences for institutional policies and practices, and provides ideas for cultivating a healthier, more engaged workforce. The following themes are generated from the gathered data.

Table 1. Gallup’s employee engagement work

Item	Mean	SD
Do you know what is expected of you at work?	4.47	0.67
Do you have the materials and equipment to do your work right?	4.27	0.93
At work, do you have the opportunity to do what you do best every day?	4.55	0.60
In the last seven days, have you received recognition or praise for doing good work?	3.80	1.09
Does your supervisor, or someone at work, seem to care about you as a person?	4.57	0.69
Is there someone at work who encourages your development?	4.44	0.72
At work, do your opinions seem to count?	4.41	0.65
Does the mission/purpose of your company make you feel your job is important?	4.45	0.60
Are your associates (fellow employees) committed to doing quality work?	4.53	0.66
Do you have a best friend at work?	4.15	0.85
In the last six months, has someone at work talked to you about your progress?	4.23	0.78
In the last year, have you had opportunities to learn and grow?	4.40	0.71
Composite mean	4.36	

3.2. Determinants affecting the well-being of university administrative employee

Communication with clients and stakeholders is highlighted as an essential element in fostering a positive work culture. Engaging with clients and stakeholders, particularly those of higher standing or influence within the organization, not only enhances job performance but also provides learning opportunities. Effective communication supports the development of both professional and social skills. One participant expressed:

“I think the most important aspect of my job is to be able to communicate with different people at all times, especially not just ordinary people but also well-respected individuals in the institution. Thus, I can learn from them and apply that knowledge to my work and daily life, especially in socializing with others outside the workplace.” (Female, 27)

Meanwhile, achieving work-life balance is key to employee satisfaction. Participants note that when work is balanced with personal life, their sense of fulfillment and well-being improves. Having time for both professional contributions and personal needs fosters a more productive and satisfied workforce. It supports the statement

“I feel most fulfilled when I can contribute meaningfully to the team, achieve work-life balance, and work in a supportive and respectful environment.” (Female, 34)

Moreover, a positive work environment and culture play a critical role in cultivating a healthy culture. Employee’s value working in environments that are respectful, inclusive, and safe. Positive relationships with colleagues also contribute significantly to a healthy work culture. The ability to handle diverse clients and situations further strengthens interpersonal skills and workplace dynamics. One participant is mentioned that:

“... a healthy work environment, a positive, safe and inclusive workplace, contributes to overall mental and emotional health.” (Female, 40)

Additionally, career development and learning opportunities, such as learning new skills and adapting to evolving work environments, are seen as essential for both personal and professional growth. Participants highlight the importance of providing learning opportunities that support growth, which contributes to job satisfaction and retention. As mentioned by the participant:

“Helping our clients with their concerns and having opportunities for growth through learning new skills.” (Female, 35)

Simultaneously, administrative and organizational support, such as managing time records, is part of the routine work that contributes to a structured and organized work environment. Organizational systems that ensure smooth operations and proper work management enhance the overall work experience. This claim was based on the participants' statement that *“a daily transaction to an employee, especially my duties as an individual in question is the administrator of the university's daily time record.”* The university can cultivate a healthy and sustainable work culture for its employees by enhancing communication, supporting work-life balance, and providing growth opportunities.

3.3. Difficulties, conditions, and coping mechanisms of administrative employees

Administrative employees face challenges including managing confidentiality, heavy workloads, time constraints, and workplace conflicts, which can hinder communication and increase stress. To cope, they prioritize tasks, stay organized, and seek collegial support. Humor, collaboration, emotional regulation, and work-life balance help maintain productivity and well-being. A supportive workplace culture enhances communication, job satisfaction, and efficiency.

3.3.1. Difficulties and conditions experienced by administrative employees

Confidentiality and managing expectations of stakeholders can pose significant communication challenges. Participants are careful in balancing privacy concerns with the need to provide quality service, often navigating complex or high-stakes communication scenarios. One participant (male, 31) stated that *“handling confidential information and managing expectations.”* The participants emphasized the importance of stress and time management. Heavy workloads and time constraints create stress that hinders effective communication. Participants often face challenges when they have to balance multiple tasks, manage deadlines, and maintain clear communication under pressure, which was supported by the statement

“Time management and heavy workloads can be stressful, along with navigating unclear instructions or communication gaps.” (Female, 34)

Additionally, interpersonal conflicts, whether with co-workers or customers, are common communication issues in the workplace. Dealing with employees who fail to follow rules or maintain appropriate behavior can create communication barriers, affecting team dynamics and service delivery. A female participant stated that *“conflicts with co-workers.”*

3.3.2. Coping mechanism to manage challenges in day-to-day work

The participants emphasized task prioritization and organization. The importance of staying organized and prioritizing tasks to manage workload effectively. These strategies allow them to maintain productivity and reduce stress, facilitating better communication and collaboration. One of the participant (female, 34) noted:

“I prioritize tasks, stay organized, and take short breaks to recharge. Talking to colleagues and finding humor during the day helps too.”

Likewise, collaboration and collegial support are also highlighted, in which humor and camaraderie among colleagues are key elements that foster positive communication and create a supportive work environment. Sharing light moments and collaboration help in navigating workplace challenges. The participant (male, 44) mentioned that:

“The best coping mechanism I had is my colleague, because we just laugh at every single detail we encounter in the office.”

Simultaneously, emotional regulation and relaxation techniques highlight by the participants the value of maintaining a calm demeanor, humility, and practicing relaxation techniques to manage workplace communication effectively. Emotional regulation helps individuals navigate difficult conversations and interactions. A 30-year-old male participant expressed the importance of “focusing on my work and engaging with relaxation techniques.” Establishing clear work-life boundaries and incorporating regular breaks are essential strategies that enable individuals to recharge and maintain effective communication during work hours. As one participant (female, 42) shared, “*I prioritize tasks, stay organized, and take short breaks to recharge.*” Similarly, maintaining focus and commitment to one’s role by fulfilling job responsibilities and meeting workplace expectations fosters trust and strengthens communication. This is reflected in another participant (male, 31) statement “*I’ll just do my best at my job.*” The findings highlight the importance of creating a work environment that promotes seamless communication, ultimately enhancing productivity and employee satisfaction. By implementing these strategies, organizations can cultivate a positive and communicative workplace culture that benefits both individuals and the company as a whole.

3.4. Engagement and well-being levels of administrative employees

This examines how employees perceive their work engagement and its impact on their overall well-being. Work engagement reflects motivation and dedication, while well-being encompasses physical, mental, and emotional health. A positive balance between these factors enhances job satisfaction, productivity, and workplace harmony.

3.4.1. Perception of oneself of work engagement levels

High engagement and commitment to quality work are central to participants’ professional dedication, as they strive to deliver excellent results and consistently exceed expectations. This strong sense of responsibility drives them to maintain high-quality output and actively contribute to their work environment. One participant expressed:

“My level of engagement in my work is high. I am fully committed to providing thoughtful, accurate, and helpful responses. I strive to understand the user’s needs and offer relevant, insightful support for each unique situation” (Female, 43)

Closely linked to engagement is the pursuit of continual learning and professional growth. Participants recognize the importance of skill enhancement and view learning as an integral part of their roles, reinforcing both job satisfaction and motivation. A participant noted:

“I can really tell that I am doing my job right. It is really on my mind to do my job accordingly since it is the work that I am paid for, and it is also a continuous learning for me.” (Female, 27)
“I’m committed to continuous learning, frequently seeking out training and development opportunities to enhance my skills and contribute more effectively.” (Female, 40)

However, engagement levels can fluctuate due to external factors such as workload and recognition. While some participants feel a consistent sense of commitment, others acknowledge that their motivation and performance are influenced by these aspects. One participant shared:

“I’m generally engaged, but it can fluctuate depending on workload and recognition for my efforts.” (Female, 34)

These ideas show how dynamic workplace engagement is and how important it is to have structures that support motivation, acknowledge contributions, and promote professional growth in order to keep commitment and productivity high.

3.4.2. The interaction between employee engagement and general well-being

Professional growth and skill development are closely linked to engagement, as active participation in the workplace enhances both individual competencies and organizational success. Lifelong learning fosters career progression and personal fulfillment, making engagement a key driver of job satisfaction and confidence. Participants emphasize that active involvement in their roles positively impacts their professional development and ability to contribute meaningfully to their organizations. As one participant noted:

“I think it is a big impact for me because, as a person, we all want to grow professionally and increase our skills to contribute to a higher level of work engagement.” (Male, 31)

Beyond skill development, engagement serves as a powerful source of motivation and purpose, helping employees feel valued and accomplished. A lack of engagement, on the other hand, can lead to fatigue and demoralization. Expressing appreciation for employees' efforts boosts morale, reinforcing their sense of purpose and dedication. One participant (female, 34) shared, *"When I'm engaged, I feel motivated and valued, which boosts my morale. Low engagement, however, can leave me drained."*

In addition to motivation, engagement plays a crucial role in fostering workplace relationships and collaboration. A culture of kindness, respect, and cooperation strengthens teams and can even extend beyond professional settings, reinforcing personal connections. Trust and mutual support contribute to both professional success and personal well-being. One participant expressed:

"Being kind and good to everybody is a good part of my job. I don't want anyone to get mad at me since I don't do things that might hurt them. I am just doing my job, my role as stated."
(Female, 27)

While engagement enhances job performance and satisfaction, it can also present challenges to work-life balance, particularly in maintaining quality time with family. Managing workloads effectively is essential to preventing burnout and ensuring equilibrium between professional and personal responsibilities. Some participants highlighted this struggle, stating:

"Positively on my work performance and skills enhancement but negatively on my family time."
(Female, 50)
"In job satisfaction, stress levels, work-life balance, motivation, and energy" (Female, 40)

Lastly, mental and emotional well-being are significantly influenced by engagement levels. High involvement in work can lead to greater job satisfaction and reduced stress, promoting emotional stability. However, insufficient engagement or excessive demands may result in stress and emotional exhaustion, making it essential to maintain a balance between professional responsibilities and self-care. As participants noted, *"good mental health"* (female, 26) and *"the university provides counseling and mental health services"* (female, 43). These insights underscore the importance of fostering an engaging, supportive, and balanced work environment to sustain both individual well-being and organizational success.

Engaged workers balance quality work, constant learning, and external influences like workload and recognition. Most admit their strong dedication to their roles, yet involvement fluctuates due to personal growth possibilities and workplace relationships. Offering learning, rewarding contributions, and managing workloads can keep employees engaged. Engagement is linked to professional development, motivation, collaboration, work-life balance, and mental health. Engagement promotes growth, satisfaction, and harmony, but it can drain time. To increase participation, organizations should promote purpose, cooperation, and mental health while addressing work-life balance.

3.5. Discussion

The study found that the well-being and engagement of university administrative employees significantly contribute to productivity, job satisfaction, and organizational efficiency. Key factors influencing well-being include effective communication, work-life balance, positive work environments, opportunities for professional growth, and stress management. Employees who feel respected and supported are more likely to be engaged, leading to improved performance and job satisfaction.

Gallup's employee engagement survey results reinforce that a composite mean score of 4.36 indicating moderate to high engagement levels. High-scoring factors, such as supervisors demonstrating genuine concern (mean: 4.57) and employees having opportunities to utilize their skills effectively (mean: 4.55), suggest that institutions foster positive interpersonal relationships and career development. Kahn's engagement theory supports this, emphasizing that meaningful work, supportive leadership, and psychological safety enhance employee engagement [15]. However, a key gap in recognition practices was identified, with the lowest mean score (3.80) reflecting a lack of acknowledgment or praise. The high standard deviation (1.09) suggests inconsistencies in recognition across departments, possibly due to varying managerial approaches. Research indicates that recognition and feedback are crucial for sustaining motivation and engagement [16], [17]. A lack of acknowledgment may lead employees to feel undervalued, diminishing their commitment and overall job satisfaction.

Qualitative data support these patterns, highlighting that excessive workloads, insufficient recognition, and interpersonal conflicts are primary stressors affecting well-being and engagement. Research shows that high job demands coupled with insufficient resources contribute to burnout, reducing both engagement and productivity [18], [19]. Employees adopt various coping mechanisms, including task prioritization, emotional regulation, peer support, and work-life boundaries. These strategies align with the

job demands-resources (JD-R) model [20], which posits that engagement is driven by balancing job demands with adequate resources. The data also show a strong relationship between well-being and engagement, with high involvement linked to improved mental health, stronger workplace relationships, and career advancement [21]. Conversely, poor well-being is associated with increased burnout, absenteeism, and employee turnover [22]. Implementing well-being initiatives, such as mental health programs, professional development opportunities, and work-life balance policies, has been shown to enhance engagement and organizational productivity [23].

The study underscores the need for universities to prioritize well-being and engagement through targeted strategies. Research suggests that effective wellness programs require strong communication, leadership involvement, and continuous evaluation [24]. Organizational support plays a crucial role in mitigating workplace stressors, aligning with the JD-R model's assertion that sufficient resources foster engagement [25]. Engaged employees demonstrate resilience in overcoming workplace challenges [26], while mental health concerns [27] and inadequate job resources [28] hinder engagement. Strong institutional support systems, including structured recovery strategies such as mindfulness practices and scheduled breaks, significantly improve well-being and engagement [29].

Recognizing these challenges, universities have increasingly implemented well-being and engagement programs to enhance employee satisfaction and productivity. Initiatives such as therapy sessions, mindfulness training, and stress management workshops provide employees with tools to manage job pressures [30]. Additionally, conflict resolution programs and team-building activities foster trust and collaboration within departments [31]. Flexible work arrangements and structured wellness programs help prevent burnout while maintaining institutional commitment [32]. Self-determination theory further emphasizes that work environments should fulfill employees' psychological needs for autonomy, competence, and relatedness [33]. Career development initiatives, including ongoing training, professional growth opportunities, and structured recognition systems, also enhance engagement [34].

A comprehensive institutional approach integrating well-being and engagement strategies is essential for long-term organizational success. Establishing clear communication channels, structured wellness programs, and continuous feedback mechanisms ensures that employees feel valued and motivated. Universities can cultivate a resilient and high-performing workforce that drives institutional efficiency and sustainability by fostering a supportive and engaging work environment.

3.6. Implications for policy and practice

One significant outcome of this study is that workplace well-being policies improve employee engagement, productivity, and institutional commitment. Professional development programs, wellness activities, and flexible work arrangements are all good, but their effectiveness might be limited by imprecise implementation, a lack of systematic acknowledgment, and office politics. Policy changes must address these gaps in order to improve employee morale, retention, and workplace satisfaction. Workplace improvements can be made fast through systematic stress management training, visible recognition systems, and improved well-being resource communication. For lasting and meaningful change, long-term systemic reforms are needed. These include creating a centralized platform for well-being resources, making recognition and incentive systems fairer, and involving employees strategically in policymaking. The long-term impact of employee well-being policies on institutional performance, retention, and job satisfaction should be investigated. Office politics and bureaucratic inefficiencies should also be investigated for their impact on employee disengagement and turnover. Leadership's role in fostering an inclusive, supportive, and psychologically safe workplace should also be investigated. Addressing these concerns allows policymakers and institutional leaders to create evidence-based policies that increase employee engagement, well-being, and organizational success.

4. CONCLUSION

The survey indicates strong employee involvement, notably in personal care and skills use. Addressing recognition and feedback issues can greatly enhance employee satisfaction. These principles help organizations encourage and engage employees, improving performance, satisfaction, and retention. A supportive and engaging administrative environment requires excellent communication, work-life balance, and professional advancement, according to the survey. Wellness programs are crucial, but stress management, recognition, and communication require improvement. Specific techniques can assist the institution in building healthier, more resilient, and engaged employees. They boost employee and institutional performance and foster a healthy workplace. University rules also promote effective communication, work-life balance, and professional development in a friendly and engaging workplace, according to the report. Stress management, recognition, and communication need improvement, although

present initiatives are welcome. Administrative employee well-being and engagement can increase productivity and morale for both employees and the institution with targeted strategies. Future research might look into how well-being programs improve employee retention and institutional success over time. Longitudinal study could reveal how engagement and well-being evolve. Comparative studies of public and private institutions may reveal unique challenges and successful strategies. Further research might look into how digital tools and technology-driven interventions increase employee engagement and minimize workplace stress. Finally, qualitative research on employee narratives and lived experiences can shed light on the challenges and potential solutions that university administration staff face.

FUNDING INFORMATION

This research received funding from a grant provided by the university, which is gratefully acknowledged.

AUTHOR CONTRIBUTIONS STATEMENT

This journal uses the Contributor Roles Taxonomy (CRediT) to recognize individual author contributions, reduce authorship disputes, and facilitate collaboration.

Name of Author	C	M	So	Va	Fo	I	R	D	O	E	Vi	Su	P	Fu
John Michael D. Aquino	✓		✓	✓	✓	✓	✓		✓		✓		✓	✓
Jayson L. De Vera	✓	✓	✓		✓		✓	✓		✓		✓	✓	✓

C : **C**onceptualization

M : **M**ethodology

So : **S**oftware

Va : **V**alidation

Fo : **F**ormal analysis

I : **I**nvestigation

R : **R**esources

D : **D**ata Curation

O : Writing - **O**riginal Draft

E : Writing - Review & **E**ditng

Vi : **V**isualization

Su : **S**upervision

P : **P**roject administration

Fu : **F**unding acquisition

CONFLICT OF INTEREST STATEMENT

The authors assert the absence of conflict of interests.

INFORMED CONSENT

All individuals granted informed consent before their participation in the study.

ETHICS STATEMENT

This work adhered to ethical guidelines and obtained approval from the Research Ethics Committee of the first author's institution (REC Code: 2024-098).

DATA AVAILABILITY

The data underpinning the conclusions of this study can be obtained upon reasonable request from the corresponding author [JMDA].

REFERENCES

- [1] D. E. Guest, "Human resource management and employee well-being: towards a new analytic framework," *Human Resource Management Journal*, vol. 27, no. 1, pp. 22–38, Jan. 2017, doi: 10.1111/1748-8583.12139.
- [2] C. Truss, A. Shantz, E. Soane, K. Alfes, and R. Delbridge, "Employee engagement, organisational performance and individual well-being: exploring the evidence, developing the theory," *The International Journal of Human Resource Management*, vol. 24, no. 14, pp. 2657–2669, Jul. 2013, doi: 10.1080/09585192.2013.798921.
- [3] B.-K. Joo and I. Lee, "Workplace happiness: work engagement, career satisfaction, and subjective well-being," *Evidence-based HRM: a Global Forum for Empirical Scholarship*, vol. 5, no. 2, pp. 206–221, Aug. 2017, doi: 10.1108/EBHRM-04-2015-0011.
- [4] Y. Brunetto, K. Shacklock, S. Teo, and R. Farr-Wharton, "The impact of management on the engagement and well-being of high emotional labour employees," *The International Journal of Human Resource Management*, vol. 25, no. 17, pp. 2345–2363, Sep. 2014, doi: 10.1080/09585192.2013.877056.
- [5] B. Shuck and A. M. Herd, "Employee engagement and leadership: Exploring the convergence of two frameworks and implications for leadership development in HRD," *Human Resource Development Review*, vol. 11, no. 2, pp. 156–181, Jun. 2012, doi: 10.1177/1534484312438211.

- [6] S. Noor, A. Aslam, and F. Md Isa, "Causes of occupational stress and burnout amongst administrative staff in public universities: case of Pakistan," *Journal of Applied Research in Higher Education*, Jul. 2024, doi: 10.1108/JARHE-03-2024-0120.
- [7] N. Bennett and T. Moore, "Developing the next generation of university leaders: An exploration of leadership development programs for professional staff," *Journal of Higher Education Policy and Management*, vol. 39, no. 6, pp. 604–618, 2017.
- [8] G. Griffin, "The 'Work-Work Balance' in higher education: between over-work, falling short and the pleasures of multiplicity," *Studies in Higher Education*, vol. 47, no. 11, pp. 2190–2203, Nov. 2022, doi: 10.1080/03075079.2021.2020750.
- [9] A. R. Szromek and R. Wolniak, "Job Satisfaction and Problems among Academic Staff in Higher Education," *Sustainability*, vol. 12, no. 12, p. 4865, Jun. 2020, doi: 10.3390/su12124865.
- [10] P. Baxter and S. Jack, "Qualitative case study methodology: Study design and implementation for novice researchers," *The Qualitative Report*, vol. 13, no. 4, pp. 544–559, 2015, doi: 10.46743/2160-3715/2008.1573.
- [11] J. Gerring, "Qualitative methods," *Annual Review of Political Science*, vol. 20, no. 1, pp. 15–36, May 2017, doi: 10.1146/annurev-polisci-092415-024158.
- [12] Z. Zhang, T. Sangsawang, K. Vipahasna, and M. Pigultong, "A mixed-methods data approach integrating importance-performance analysis (IPA) and Kaiser-Meyer-Olkin (KMO) in applied talent cultivation," *Journal of Applied Data Sciences*, vol. 5, no. 1, pp. 256–267, Jan. 2024, doi: 10.47738/jads.v5i1.170.
- [13] R. Khanna, "Re-explore the viability and authenticity of Gallup workplace audit in private university," *Business Management and Education*, vol. 18, no. 2, pp. 344–362, 2020, doi: 10.3846/bme.2020.11999.
- [14] Gallup, "Gallup - Workplace consulting & global research," 2019. [Online]. Available: <https://www.gallup.com/home.aspx>
- [15] J. Mao and K. Tian, "Psychological safety mediates the relationship between leader-member exchange and employees' work engagement," *Social Behavior and Personality*, vol. 50, no. 3, pp. 31–39, Mar. 2022, doi: 10.2224/sbp.11266.
- [16] A. B. Bakker and J. D. de Vries, "Job Demands-Resources theory and self-regulation: new explanations and remedies for job burnout," *Anxiety, Stress and Coping*, vol. 34, no. 1, pp. 1–21, Jan. 2021, doi: 10.1080/10615806.2020.1797695.
- [17] S. Gürbüz, A. B. Bakker, E. Demerouti, and E. P. M. Brouwers, "Sustainable employability and work engagement: a three-wave study," *Frontiers in Psychology*, vol. 14, p. 1188728, Jun. 2023, doi: 10.3389/fpsyg.2023.1188728.
- [18] J. M. D. Aquino and M. G. Reyes, "COVID-19 and well-being of tertiary students in one state university: basis for social counseling program," *International Journal of Social Learning (IJSLS)*, vol. 4, no. 2, pp. 180–196, Apr. 2024, doi: 10.47134/ijsl.v4i2.222.
- [19] W. B. Schaufeli, "Applying the Job Demands-Resources model: A 'how to' guide to measuring and tackling work engagement and burnout," *Organizational Dynamics*, vol. 46, no. 2, pp. 120–132, Apr. 2017, doi: 10.1016/j.orgdyn.2017.04.008.
- [20] M. Roskams, E. McNeely, D. Weziak-Bialowolska, and P. Bialowolski, "Job Demands-Resources Model: Its applicability to the workplace environment and human flourishing," in *A Handbook of Theories on Designing Alignment Between People and the Office Environment*, R. Appel-Meulenbroek and V. Danivska, Eds., New York: Routledge, 2021, pp. 27–38, doi: 10.1177/20413866221135022.
- [21] N. Jones, G. B. Teague, J. Wolf, and C. Rosen, "Organizational climate and support among peer specialists working in peer-run, hybrid, and conventional mental health settings," *Administration and Policy in Mental Health and Mental Health Services Research*, vol. 47, no. 1, pp. 150–167, Jan. 2020, doi: 10.1007/s10488-019-00980-9.
- [22] C. Gerhardt et al., "How are social stressors at work related to well-being and health? A systematic review and meta-analysis," *BMC Public Health*, vol. 21, no. 1, p. 890, Dec. 2021, doi: 10.1186/s12889-021-10894-7.
- [23] J. M. D. Aquino, I. P. Palad, and A. P. Simbre, "Filipino teachers' aspiration on their personal and professional development," *AHEAD Journal*, vol. 1, no. 1, pp. 101–114, 2023.
- [24] D. G. Passey, K. Hammerback, A. Huff, J. R. Harris, and P. A. Hannon, "The Role of Managers in Employee Wellness Programs: A Mixed-Methods Study," *American Journal of Health Promotion*, vol. 32, no. 8, pp. 1697–1705, Nov. 2018, doi: 10.1177/0890117118767785.
- [25] Y. Wang, "Exploring the impact of workload, organizational support, and work engagement on teachers' psychological wellbeing: a structural equation modeling approach," *Frontiers in Psychology*, vol. 14, p. 1345740, Jan. 2023, doi: 10.3389/fpsyg.2023.1345740.
- [26] J. R. C. Kuntz, S. Malinen, and K. Näswall, "Employee resilience: Directions for resilience development," *Consulting Psychology Journal: Practice and Research*, vol. 69, no. 3, pp. 223–242, Sep. 2017, doi: 10.1037/cpb0000097.
- [27] C. Ammendolia et al., "Healthy and productive workers: Using intervention mapping to design a workplace health promotion and wellness program to improve presenteeism," *BMC Public Health*, vol. 16, no. 1, pp. 1–18, Dec. 2016, doi: 10.1186/s12889-016-3843-x.
- [28] E. Cabrera-Aguilar et al., "Resilience and stress as predictors of work engagement: the mediating role of self-efficacy in nurses," *Frontiers in Psychiatry*, vol. 14, p. 1202048, Aug. 2023, doi: 10.3389/fpsyg.2023.1202048.
- [29] D. B. Newman, L. Tay, and E. Diener, "Leisure and subjective well-being: A model of psychological mechanisms as mediating factors," *Journal of Happiness Studies*, vol. 15, no. 3, pp. 555–578, Jun. 2014, doi: 10.1007/s10902-013-9435-x.
- [30] A. B. Bakker, E. Demerouti, and A. I. Sanz-Vergel, "Burnout and work engagement: the JDR approach," *Annual Review of Organizational Psychology and Organizational Behavior*, vol. 1, no. 1, pp. 389–411, Mar. 2014, doi: 10.1146/annurev-orgpsych-031413-091235.
- [31] Dr. Illavarasi, "Enhancing workplace productivity: a review of effective communication techniques and their role in fostering team collaboration and conflict resolution," *International Journal for Multidimensional Research Perspectives*, vol. 2, no. 4, pp. 33–45, Apr. 2024, doi: 10.61877/ijmrp.v2i4.132.
- [32] M. A. Mulvaney, "Leave programs/time off and work-stress family employee benefits programs, organizational commitment, and self-efficacy among municipal employees," *Public Personnel Management*, vol. 43, no. 4, pp. 459–489, Dec. 2014, doi: 10.1177/0091026014529661.
- [33] E. L. Deci, A. H. Olafsen, and R. M. Ryan, "Self-determination theory in work organizations: The state of a science," *Annual Review of Organizational Psychology and Organizational Behavior*, vol. 4, no. 1, pp. 19–43, Mar. 2017, doi: 10.1146/annurev-orgpsych-032516-113108.
- [34] C. Hughes, Y. Niu, and T. W. Greer, "Opportunities in VR career development," in *Career Development and Virtual Remote Work: Challenges and Opportunities*, C. Hughes, Y. Niu, and T. W. Greer, Eds., Cham: Palgrave Macmillan, 2025, pp. 93–118, doi: 10.1007/978-3-031-75899-7_5.

BIOGRAPHIES OF AUTHORS

John Michael D. Aquino graduated doctor of Philosophy in Educational Leadership and Management at the Philippine Normal University in Manila. He has published and presented articles in international and local journals in the disciplines of physical education, leadership and management, and social sciences, and is a regular member of the National Research Council of the Philippines. Likewise, he is a full-time faculty member at Laguna State Polytechnic University. He can be contacted at email: johnmichael.aquino@lspu.edu.ph.

Jayson L. de Vera is an experienced educator, researcher, and academic leader dedicated to advancing science education and pedagogy in the Philippines and beyond. He currently serves as an assistant professor of Science Education in the Faculty of Science, Technology, and Mathematics at the Philippine Normal University. Additionally, he has served as a reviewer for academic publications, a panelist for research defenses, and a member of professional organizations such as the National Research Council of the Philippines. He can be contacted at email: devera.jl@pnu.edu.ph.